

COMPARATIVE DIAGNOSTIC PERFORMANCE OF NITRITE AND LEUKOCYTE ESTERASE TESTS WITH URINE CULTURE FOR ASYMPTOMATIC BACTERIURIA SCREENING IN PREGNANCY

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Abstract

Background: Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ABU) during pregnancy is associated with many complications for both the fetus and the mother, including miscarriage, preterm labor, hypertension, pyelonephritis, renal failure, and even death. Early detection of urinary tract infection (UTI) using nitrite (N.) and leukocyte esterase (LE) dipstick testing can help reduce these complications. **Objective:** To evaluate the role of nitrite (N.) and leukocyte esterase (LE) dipstick tests compared to urine culture for the detection of ABU in pregnant women. **Study Design:** Prospective study. **Setting:** Department of Gynaecology & Obstetrics, Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital, over a period of one year from September 2023 to September 2024. **Materials and Methods:** A clean-catch midstream urine specimen was obtained from 500 pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic at Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital. One portion of the specimen was tested for nitrite (N.) and leukocyte esterase (LE.) activity using a dipstick. The second portion was plated on blood and MacConkey agars for culture, and the third portion was used for microscopical examination (ME). The results of the above-mentioned tests were compared. **Results:** ABU was prevalent in 12% (60/500) of the pregnant women evaluated. The nitrite (N.) test demonstrated 68.3% sensitivity (SN) and 100% specificity (SP), while the leukocyte esterase (LE) test showed 53.3% SN and 99.5% SP. Both were considered acceptable tests in comparison with urine culture. The predominant microorganism isolated was *E. coli*. **Conclusion:** The nitrite (N.) and leukocyte esterase (LE.) tests had high specificity and negative predictive value (NPV) compared to urine culture for the detection of ABU. However, the nitrite (N.) test was more sensitive and specific than the leukocyte esterase (LE.) test. In the current study, all cases that were positive on the nitrite test were also positive on urine culture, supporting its utility as a screening test for ABU.

Keywords: Nitrite & leukocyte esterase dipstick tests, pregnant women, UTI & ABU.

Introduction:

UTIs are among the most common bacterial infections in women, occurring from the neonatal period through the geriatric age group. Half of all women experience at least one UTI in their lifetime⁽¹⁾. Most UTIs in women are acute, uncomplicated cystitis caused by *E. Coli*⁽²⁾. Pregnancy increases the likelihood of kidney involvement (pyelonephritis), with an incidence of around 20-40% in affected women⁽³⁾. If this condition is not treated in pregnant women with ABU, they are 4 times more likely to develop a symptomatic UTI than women without this condition, and associated with pyelonephritis, premature delivery and low birth weight. Pyelonephritis may occur because of the mechanical effect of urinary tract compression and/or smooth muscle relaxation in pregnancy together with UTI which may be symptomatic or asymptomatic^(4,5). There is an association between untreated ABU, low birth weight, preterm birth, pregnancy-associated hypertension and anemia⁽⁶⁾. However, while a reduction in preterm birth and low birth weight is consistent with understanding of the role of infection in pregnancy complications⁽⁷⁾.

Only few antibiotics can be safely used. Oral β -lactams, sulfonamides, and nitrofurantoin are considered safe in early pregnancy, but trimethoprim (TMP) should be avoided during the 1st trimester, and sulfamethoxazole (SMX) should be avoided during the 3rd trimester, particularly near parturition. Patients with untreatable obstructive problems (e.g. calculi and reflux) may require long-term suppressive therapy. Outpatient man-

agement can be considered in pregnant women with pyelonephritis, but only if symptoms are mild, close follow-up is available, and the pregnancy is < 24 weeks of gestation. Outpatient treatment is with cephalosporins (e.g., ceftriaxone 1 to 2 grams (g) intravenous (IV) or intramuscular (IM), then cephalexin 500 mg four times daily for 10 days). Otherwise, 1st-line antibiotics include cephalosporins and aztreonam. Hospitalisation, IV hydration to achieve adequate urinary output, and antipyretics may be required. Antibiotic therapy for 2 weeks followed by suppressive therapy for the remainder of the pregnancy. Recurrence rate is approximately 20%^(6,8). If pyelonephritis is severe, possibilities include piperacillin/tazobactam or meropenem. Fluoroquinolones, TMP & SMX should be avoided, because recurrence is common. Some authorities recommend prophylaxis after the acute infection resolves, with nitrofurantoin 100 mg twice daily or cephalexin 250 mg every night for the remainder of pregnancy and for 4 to 6 weeks after pregnancy⁽⁹⁾.

Aim of the study: To correlate the effect of N. & LE in dipstick with the urine culture in the detection of ABU in pregnant women.

Patients and Methods

A **prospective study** was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at **Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital, Baghdad, Iraq**, over one year from **September 2023 to September 2024**. Ethical approval was obtained from the **Arab Board for Medical Specialization** and the hospital's Scientific Research

Committee, and **verbal informed consent** was obtained from all participants.

The study included **500 pregnant women** attending the antenatal outpatient clinic. Women of **any gestational age, maternal age, parity, and educational level** were eligible. Exclusion criteria included **amniotic fluid leakage, vaginal bleeding, recent antibiotic use (within one week), and active labour**. Demographic and clinical information, including maternal age, gravidity, parity, and relevant obstetric, gynecological, medical, and surgical histories, was recorded. Gestational age was determined from the last menstrual period (LMP) and confirmed by ultrasonography, followed by a complete general and obstetric examination.

Urine collection:

For urine collection, participants provided a **10–15 mL clean-catch midstream urine sample** after cleansing the perineal area with clean water and separating the labia minora. Samples were collected in sterile containers and analysed within **30 minutes**. The clean-catch technique was used to minimize contamination from vaginal flora. Alternative collection methods, such as suprapubic aspiration and urethral catheterisation, were discussed but not routinely employed due to their invasive nature and potential complications.

Urinary tract infection (UTI) was assessed using three diagnostic methods:

1. **Dipstick testing for leukocyte esterase (LE) and nitrite (N)**, providing a rapid screening tool for bacteriuria and pyuria.
2. **Microscopic examination of urine sediment**, where the presence of **≥10 white blood cells (WBC)/high-power field (HPF)** indicated pyuria and **1–10 microorganisms/HPF** suggested bacteriuria.
3. **Urine culture** is considered the reference diagnostic method. Urine specimens were inoculated onto **MacConkey and blood agar media** and incubated at **37°C for 24 hours**. Samples delayed for more than two hours before analysis were stored at **4°C** to prevent bacterial overgrowth.

For laboratory analysis, **3–5 mL of fresh urine** was used for dipstick testing, **0.1 mL** was cultured using standard microbiological techniques, and the remaining sample was centrifuged for microscopic evaluation. Pyuria was defined as **≥10 WBC/mm³**, and the presence of bacteria under oil-immersion microscopy was considered evidence of bacteriuria. Finally, the diagnostic performance of **nitrite and leukocyte esterase dipstick tests** was compared with **urine culture results** to evaluate their effectiveness in detecting urinary

tract infection during pregnancy. All laboratory investigations were performed at the **Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital Laboratory Centre**.

A prospective study involving **500 pregnant women** attending the antenatal clinic of Al-Yarmouk Teaching Hospital, Baghdad, was conducted between September 2013 and September 2014. Eligible participants included pregnant women of any gestational age, parity, or age, while those with vaginal bleeding, amniotic fluid leakage, recent antibiotic use, or active labor were excluded. Clean-catch midstream urine samples were collected under standardised conditions and analysed within 30 minutes. UTI diagnosis was performed using **dipstick testing (nitrite and leukocyte esterase), urine microscopy, and urine culture**. Urine culture on MacConkey and blood agar served as the reference standard. Microscopic examination identified pyuria and bacteriuria, while dipstick findings were compared with culture results to assess the diagnostic accuracy of nitrite and leukocyte esterase testing in pregnant women.

Statistical Analysis:

All collected data were coded and analysed using the **Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA)**. Categorical variables were summarised as frequencies and percentages and compared using the **Pearson chi-square test**. Continuous variables were expressed as **mean ± standard deviation (SD)** and compared using the **independent-samples t-test**. The diagnostic validity of urine dipstick tests was assessed by calculating **sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy**, with urine culture considered the gold standard for diagnosis. Statistical significance was defined as a **two-tailed p-value of less than 0.05**.

Results:

500 pregnant women have been included in this study, assessed for UTI in symptomatic and asymptomatic women. Results in Table 1 showed the association between the demographic characteristics of patients. It appears that there is a significant relationship between positive urine culture with GA and a previous history of miscarriage. By using Pearson's chi-square test, the p-value was 0.002 with GA and 0.001 with a history of miscarriages.

Table 1:

Demographic characteristics of the study groups, n=500

Parameters	Urinary tract infection		p-value ^a
	Overall UTI (n=70) Mean±(SD)	No UTI (n=430) Mean±(SD)	
Age (years)	28.7±(4.3)	29.1±(4.9)	0.520 (NS)
Gestational age (weeks)	9.3±(1.3)	9.7±(1.5)	0.012*
	No. (%)	No. (%)	p-value ^b
Parity	≤ 1	31 (44.3)	0.275 (NS)
	2 – 5	21 (30)	
	> 5	18 (25.7)	
Gravida	≤ 1	32 (45.7)	0.661 (NS)
	2 – 5	20 (28.6)	
	> 5	18 (25.7)	
Previous history of miscarriages	0	24 (34.3)	<0.001*
	1 – 2	34 (48.6)	
	≥ 3	12 (17.1)	

Note : results in SD= Standard deviation, a: Pearson's chi-square, b: Independent t-test, NS: not significant, * significant at $\alpha < 0.05$.

The results in Table 2 showed the bacteriological findings of 70 pregnant women with positive urine cultures. *E. coli* was the predominant cause of UTIs in this

study. It has been isolated from 50(71.4%) of the included patients.

Table 2:

The results of the urine culture among the included pregnant women, n=70.

Microorganism	No.	%
<i>E. Coli</i>	50	71.4%
<i>Klebsiella.sp</i>	10	14.3%
<i>Staph.sp.</i>	4	5.7%
<i>Monilia</i>	6	8.6%
Total	70	100%

Table 3 compares diagnostic tests performed on the 500 pregnant women included in this study. As shown, 70 out of 500 pregnant women diagnosed with UTI confirmed by urine culture, 10(14.3%) of them were symptomatic, and 60(85.7%) were asymptomatic, with a p-value of 0.35.

UTI diagnosed by N.: 47 patients of them, 6(12.8%) were symptomatic, and 41(87.2%) were asymptomatic, with a p-value of 0.72.UTI diagnosed by

LE test: 38 patients of them, 4(10.5%) were symptomatic, and 34(89.5%) were asymptomatic, with a p-value of 0.49. By using the combined test N. & LE UTI diagnosed 36 patients of them, 5(13.9%) were symptomatic and 31(86.1%) were asymptomatic with p-value 0.99. Finally, by using ME: 40 patients of them, 8(20%) were symptomatic and 32(80%) were asymptomatic with p value 0.47.

Table 3:

Comparison of positive diagnostic tests for UTI among included pregnant women according to the symptoms, n=500.

Positive tests	Symptomatic Number No. (%)	Asymptomatic No. (%)	Total	p-value
Urine Culture	10 (14.3)	60 (85.7)	70	0.35 ^P
Nitrite	6 (12.8)	41 (87.2)	47	0.72 ^F
Leukocyte esterase	4 (10.5)	34 (89.5)	38	0.49 ^F
Nitrite & leukocyte Esterase	5 (13.9)	31 (86.1)	36	0.99 ^F
Microscopic examination	8 (20)	32 (80)	40	0.47 ^F

^P Pearson's chi-square, ^F Fisher's exact test

Table 4 compares the SN, SP, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of N. with those of urine culture among 500 pregnant women. It appears that there are 5(50%) out of 10 patients with symptomatic UTI had positive N. and urine culture tests

with SN 50%, SP 99.8%, PPV 83.3% & NPV 99.8%, 41 patients out of 60 patients with asymptomatic UTI had positive N. and urine culture tests with SN 68.3%, SP 100%, PPV 100% & NPV 95.8%.

Table 4:

Comparison between the results of N. and those of the urine culture according to the symptoms, n=500.

Nitrite test	Urine Culture		Total No. (%)	SN	SP	PPV	NPV
	Positive No. (%)	Negative No. (%)					
Symptomatic							
Positive	5 (50)	1 (0.2)	6 (1.4)	50%	99.8%	83.3%	99.8%
Negative	5 (50)	429 (99.8)	434 (98.6)				
Total	10 (100)	430 (100)	440 (100)				
Asymptomatic							
Positive	41 (68.3)	0 (0)	41 (8.4)	68.3%	100%	100%	95.8%
Negative	19 (31.7)	430 (100)	449 (91.6)				
Total	60 (100)	430 (100)	490 (100)				
SN=Sensitivity, SP=Specificity, PPV=Positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value							

Table 5 compares the SN, SP, PPV & NPV of LE with those of urine culture in 500 pregnant women. It appears that 3(30%) out of 10 with symptomatic UTI had positive LE and urine culture tests with SN 30%,

SP 99.8%, PPV 75% & NPV 98.4% and 32(53.3%) out of 60 patients with asymptomatic UTI had positive LE and urine culture tests with SN 53.3%, SP 99.5%, PPV 94.1% & NPV 93.9%.

Table 5:

Comparison between the results of LE and those of the urine culture, n=500.

leukocyte esterase test	Urine Culture		Total No. (%)	SN	SP	PPV	NPV
	Positive No. (%)	Negative No. (%)					
Symptomatic							
Positive	3 (30)	1 (0.2)	4 (0.9)	30.0 %	99.8 %	75.0 %	98.4 %
Negative	7 (70)	429 (99.8)	436 (99.1)				
Total	10 (100)	430 (100)	440 (100)				
Asymptomatic							
Positive	32 (53.3)	2 (0.5)	34 (6.9)	53.3 %	99.5 %	94.1 %	93.9 %
Negative	28 (46.7)	428 (99.5)	456 (93.1)				
Total	60 (100)	430 (100)	490 (100)				
SN=Sensitivity, SP=Specificity, PPV=Positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value							

Table 6 compares the SN, SP, PPV & NPV of a combination of N. and LE with urine culture in 500 pregnant women. It appears that 4(40%) patients out of

10(100%) were symptomatic UTI had positive combined tests and urine culture tests with SN 40%, SP 99.8%, PPV 80.8% & NPV 98.6%, 31(51.7%) patients out of 60(100%)

With asymptomatic UTI, had positive combined tests and urine culture tests with SN 51.7%, SP 99.5%, PPV 93.9% and NPV 93.7%.

Table 6:

Comparison between the results of N. and LE to those of the urine culture, n=500.

Nitrite and leukocyte test	Urine Culture		Total No. (%)	SN	SP	PPV	NPV
	Positive No. (%)	Negative No. (%)					
Symptomatic							
Positive	4 (40)	1 (0.2)	5 (1.1)	40.0 %	99.8 %	80.0 %	98.6 %
Negative	6 (60)	429 (99.8)	435 (98.9)				
Total	10 (100)	430 (100)	440 (100)				
Asymptomatic							
Positive	31 (51.7)	2 (0.5)	33 (6.7)	51.7 %	99.5 %	93.9 %	93.7 %
Negative	29 (48.3)	428 (99.5)	457 (93.3)				
Total	60 (100)	430 (100)	490 (100)				
SN=Sensitivity, SP=Specificity, PPV=Positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value							

Table 7 compares the SN, SP, PPV & NPV of ME with those of urine culture in 500 pregnant women. It appears that 6(60%) out of 10(100%) with symptomatic UTI had positive ME and urine culture tests with SN 60%, SP 99.5%, PPV 75% & NPV 99.1%,

32(53.3%) out of 60(100%) patients with asymptomatic UTI had positive ME and urine culture tests with SN 53%, SP 99.5%, PPV 94.1% and NPV 93.9.

Table 7:

Comparison between the results of microscopic examination and those of the urine culture, n=500.

Microscopic examination	Urine Culture		Total No. (%)	SN	SP	PPV	NPV
	Positive No. (%)	Negative No. (%)					
Symptomatic							
Positive	6 (60)	2 (0.5)	8 (1.8)	60.0 %	99.5 %	75.0 %	99.1 %
Negative	4 (40)	428 (99.5)	432 (98.2)				
Total	10 (100)	430 (100)	440 (100)				
Asymptomatic							
Positive	32 (53.3)	2 (0.5)	34 (6.9)	53.3 %	99.5 %	94.1 %	93.9 %
Negative	28 (46.7)	428 (99.5)	456 (93.1)				
Total	60 (100)	430 (100)	490 (100)				
SN=Sensitivity, SP=Specificity, PPV=Positive predictive value, NPV=negative predictive value							

Discussion:

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is a common health problem during pregnancy due to hormonal, anatomical, and physiological changes^(10,11). Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ABU) is particularly important because early detection can prevent acute pyelonephritis,

chronic renal failure, prematurity, and fetal mortality. Although urine culture is the gold standard for ABU diagnosis, it is time-consuming and requires uncontaminated samples. A rapid, cost-effective screening test with a high negative predictive value (NPV) is therefore desirable, especially in resource-limited settings

such as Iraq. The dipstick test (nitrite and leukocyte esterase) is simple, rapid (2–5 minutes vs 2–3 days for culture), and low-cost (3,000–5,000 ID vs 20,000–30,000 ID), making it suitable for office-based screening, with confirmatory culture reserved for positive screens⁽¹²⁾.

In the present study, the overall UTI prevalence was 14%, with ABU accounting for 12%. This is comparable to Mignini et al. (15%)⁽¹³⁾ but higher than reports from Danilla et al. (10%)⁽¹⁴⁾, Paula et al.⁽¹⁵⁾, Tadesse et al. (9.8%)⁽¹⁶⁾, Turpin et al. (7.3%)⁽¹⁷⁾, and Jayalaxmi et al. (7.3%)⁽¹¹⁾. An Iranian study reported 6.3%⁽¹⁰⁾. These differences likely reflect variations in climate, healthcare access, and educational levels between developed and developing countries⁽¹⁸⁾.

A significant relationship was found between gestational age, prior miscarriages, and UTI, contrary to Kovavisarach et al.⁽¹⁹⁾ and Demilie⁽²⁰⁾, who found no trimester-related differences. No significant association was observed with maternal age or high parity, although Foxman⁽²¹⁾ and others^(22,23) reported advanced age (≥ 35 years) and multiparity as risk factors, possibly due to cumulative exposure.

E. coli was the predominant organism (71.4%), consistent with Abdullah et al. (66.7%)⁽²⁴⁾, Titoria et al. (60%)⁽²⁵⁾, and Tambekal *et al.*, (59%)⁽²⁶⁾. Lower rates were reported by Taneja *et al.*, (47%)⁽²⁷⁾, Demilie (45.7%)⁽²⁰⁾, and Danilla (40.7%)⁽¹⁴⁾. This predominance may be explained by urinary stasis in pregnancy, which favors *E. coli* growth, and poor genital hygiene⁽²⁸⁾.

Sensitivity (SN) 50%, specificity (SP) 99.8% for symptomatic UTI; 68.3% SN, 100% SP for ABU. Comparable to Demilie (57.1% SN, 96.7% SP symptomatic; 35.7% SN, 98% SP ABU)⁽²⁰⁾ and Kacmaz et al. (60% SN, 99.2% SP for ABU)⁽²⁹⁾. Kerbella reported 66.6% SN, 97.7% SP⁽¹⁸⁾. Variability may reflect differences in uropathogen prevalence and nitrate-reducing capacity⁽¹²⁾.

Leukocyte esterase (LE) test: SN 30%, SP 99.8% (symptomatic); 53.3% SN, 99.5% SP (ABU). Lower than Demilie (71% SN, 90% SP symptomatic; 50% SN, 89.1% SP ABU)⁽²⁰⁾, Kerbella (70.3% SN, 88.5% SP)⁽¹⁸⁾, and Kacmaz (70% SN, 92.5% SP)⁽²⁹⁾. Low sensitivity may be due to bladder colonisation, alkaline urine, or disintegration of pus cells. False positives can occur with ascorbic acid, albumin, or phenazopyridine^(29,30). **Combined nitrite and LE:** SN 51.7%, SP 99.5% for ABU, consistent with Mignini et al. (53% SN, 99% SP)⁽¹³⁾. Masinde et al. reported lower agreement (38.9% SN, 86.7% SP) and questioned the added benefit⁽³¹⁾. **Microscopic examination (ME):** SN 60%, SP 99.5% for symptomatic UTI; 53.3% SN, 99.5% SP for ABU. Similar to Hemeda et al. (60% SN, 62.3% SP)⁽³²⁾ and Titoria et al. (60% SN, 88% SP)⁽²⁵⁾, but lower than Kerbella (92.5% SN, 98.8% SP)⁽¹⁸⁾.

Conclusion: The N. test & LE tests had high SP & NPV, comparable to urine culture, for detecting ABU. However, N. test was more sensitive and specific than LE. In the current study, all N. test cases were positive on urine culture, indicating that it is a good test for detecting ABU. It is accurate, rapid, and less costly than urine culture. The predominant uropathogen in the current study was *E. coli*.

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